

FULL k -COMPLETE PARTITIONS

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Abstract

A partition of a positive integer is full k -complete if it contains $p(t)$ representations of every positive integer t , $1 \leq t \leq k$, where $p(n)$ is the number of all partitions of n . We study the enumeration properties of such partitions in this paper. We also discuss a further type of completeness defined by containment of perfect partitions.

1. Introduction

A *partition* of an integer $n > 0$ is a representation of n as a weakly increasing sum of positive integers. The summands are called *parts*, and n is the *weight*, of the partition.

We will denote partitions as vectors with positive-integer entries. Thus a partition of n into k parts will be generally expressed as

$$\lambda = (\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_k), \quad 0 < \lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2 \leq \dots \leq \lambda_k, \quad (1)$$

or

$$\lambda = (\lambda_1^{v_1}, \lambda_2^{v_2}, \dots, \lambda_t^{v_t}), \quad 0 < \lambda_1 < \lambda_2 < \dots < \lambda_t, \quad t \leq k, \quad (2)$$

where $v_i > 0$ denotes the multiplicity of λ_i for each i , and $v_1 + v_2 + \dots + v_t = k$. The empty partition of 0 is denoted by (0) or \emptyset .

Hoggatt and King [4] defined an arbitrary sequence $\{f_i\}_{i=1}^{\infty}$ of positive integers to be complete, if and only if every positive integer n can be represented in the form $n = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \alpha_i f_i$, where α_i is either 0 or 1. When translated to partitions, Park [9] defined a complete partition of an integer as follows.

Definition 1 ([9]). A complete partition of n is a weakly increasing partition λ with $\lambda_1 = 1$, such that each integer t , $1 \leq t \leq n$, can be expressed as a sum of elements of λ , that is, each t can be expressed as $\sum_{j=1}^k \alpha_j \lambda_j$, where α_j is either 0 or 1.

For example, of the 11 partitions of $n = 6$, five are complete partitions, namely, $(1^6), (1^33), (1^42), (123), (1^22^2)$. Subsequently Park [10] studied r -complete partitions whereby λ is said to be r -complete if each i with $1 \leq i \leq rn$ can be expressed as $\sum_{j=1}^k \alpha_j \lambda_j$, where $\alpha_j \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, r\}$. It follows that the complete partitions correspond to 1-complete partitions under the latter definition. For example, (1^4) and (1^22) are 1-complete partitions of $n = 4$, and $(1^4), (1^22)$ and $(1, 3)$ are 2-complete partitions.

In this paper we consider a more inclusive type of complete partition. The “full k -complete” partitions discussed here are complete by virtue of the fact that they contain $p(t)$ representations of every positive integer $t < k$, where $p(N)$ is the number of all partitions of N . In addition, we give brief discussions of two types of completeness according to the containment of perfect partitions called ‘perfect-partition-complete’ and ‘full-perfect-partition-complete’ partitions.

In Section 2 we explain two important notions for subsequent work. Then in Section 3 we define full k -complete partitions and explore their properties. Section 4 is devoted to a brief discussion of perfect-partition-complete partitions, followed by full-perfect-partition-complete partitions in Section 5.

2. Preliminaries

In this section we explain the essential concepts of derived partition and perfect partition. In the sequel we will also use the notation $\lambda \vdash n$ to mean that λ is a partition of n .

Definition 2. Let λ be a partition of n . A *derived partition* (or subpartition) of λ is any partition π of a nonnegative integer $m \leq n$ whose parts form a sub-multiset of the multiset of the parts of λ .

The set of derived partitions of λ will be denoted by $D(\lambda)$. It is clear that $(0) \in D(\lambda)$. So $D(\lambda) \neq \emptyset$ for all λ .

Example 1. Consider the partition $\lambda = (1, 2^2, 3) \vdash 8$. Then

$$D(\lambda) = \{(0), (1), (2), (2^2), (3), (1, 2), (1, 2^2), (1, 3), (2, 3), (2^2, 3), (1, 2, 3), \lambda\}.$$

Since λ is a partition of a finite integer n it has a finite number of derived partitions. So $D(\lambda)$ is a finite set. Moreover, in order to form a derived partition of $\lambda = (\lambda_1^{v_1}, \dots, \lambda_k^{v_k})$, one selects t copies of λ_i , where $0 \leq t \leq v_i$ for each i . Thus we have proved the following assertion.

Proposition 1. *We have $|D((\lambda_1^{v_1}, \lambda_2^{v_2}, \dots, \lambda_k^{v_k}))| = (v_1 + 1)(v_2 + 1) \cdots (v_k + 1)$.*

Thus from Example 1 we have $|D((1, 2^2, 3))| = 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 2 = 12$, as expected.

2.1. Perfect Partitions

The definition of a perfect partition first appeared in the works of P. A. MacMahon [6, 7]. Subsequently other mathematicians studied and found several properties and generalizations of perfect partitions (see for example, [1, 5, 8]).

Definition 3. *A perfect partition is a partition in which the parts contain exactly one partition of every positive integer smaller than or equal to n .*

That is, if $\lambda \vdash n$ is a perfect partition, then $D(\lambda)$ contains exactly one partition of each number from 0 to n . This implies that $|D(\lambda)| = n + 1$.

For example, $(1^3, 4) \vdash 7$ is a perfect partition since

$$D((1^3, 4)) = \{(0), (1), (1^2), (1^3), (4), (1, 4), (1^2, 4), (1^3, 4)\},$$

which contains $|D((1^3, 4))| = 8$ partitions consisting of one partition of 0, 1, ..., 7, respectively.

The enumeration of perfect partitions is facilitated by the enumeration of ordered factorizations of integers into products of factors greater than 1.

Theorem 1 (MacMahon). *The number of perfect partitions of n is the same as the number of ordered factorizations of $n + 1$ without 1's.*

Proof. Let $n + 1 = g_1 g_2 \cdots g_r$, $g_i > 1$, be an ordered factorization of $n + 1$. Then the corresponding perfect partition of n is given by

$$\lambda = \left(1^{g_1-1}, g_1^{g_2-1}, (g_1 g_2)^{g_3-1}, \dots, (g_1 g_2 \cdots g_{r-1})^{g_r-1}\right). \tag{3}$$

By summing the parts of λ in (3), one may verify that the weight of λ is n . On the other hand, we may use Proposition 1 to verify that $|D(\lambda)| = n + 1$. □

Example 2. We give the ordered factorizations of 8 which correspond to the perfect partitions of 7 in Table 1.

Perfect Partition of 7	(1^7)	$(1, 2^3)$	$(1^3, 4)$	$(1, 2, 4)$
Ord. Factorization of 8	8	$2 \cdot 4$	$4 \cdot 2$	$2 \cdot 2 \cdot 2$

Table 1: Perfect Partitions of 7 and factorizations of 8

3. Full k -Complete Partitions

Definition 4. A partition π of a positive integer is called *full k -complete* if the parts of π contain the parts of all partitions of every integer from 1 to k . Alternatively, π is full k -complete if the set $D(\pi)$ contains all partitions of every positive integer from 1 to k .

For instance, (1) is full 1-complete, $(1,1,1,2)$ and $(1,1,2,3)$ are both full 2-complete while $(1,1,1,2,3)$ is full 3-complete (and therefore full 1- and full 2-complete). A perfect partition is at most full 1-complete.

For example,

$$D((1, 1, 1, 2)) = \{(1), (1, 1), (2), (1, 1, 1), (1, 2), (1, 1, 2), (1, 1, 1, 2)\}$$

which is seen to contain every partition λ of m for $m = 1, 2$. However, $(1, 1, 1, 2)$ is not full 3-complete because $(3) \notin D((1, 1, 1, 2))$.

Let $C_k(n)$ denote the set of full k -complete partitions of n with $c_k(n) = |C_k(n)|$. Any partition $\pi \in C_k(n)$ is full j -complete, where $j = 1, 2, \dots, k$. Note that $C_k(0) = \{(0)\}$ by definition.

The set $C_k(n)$ is largest when $k = 1$ since $C_1(n)$ is the set of all partitions of n that contain 1 as a part. The union of all full k -complete partitions of n is $C_1(n)$. There is a strictly decreasing chain of sets of full k -complete partitions of n , namely

$$C_1(n) \supset C_2(n) \supset C_3(n) \supset \dots$$

An integer n has a finite number of full k -complete partitions, but there is an infinite number of full k -complete partitions for any $k > 0$. For instance, a partition of the form $(1^a, 2^b)$, $a > 1, b > 0$, is full 2-complete. Table 2 shows all members of the sets $C_i(1), C_i(2), \dots, C_i(10)$ for $i = 2, 3$.

Lemma 1. *Let π be a full k -complete partition, and let m be an integer with $1 \leq m \leq k$. Then π contains all positive integer divisors of m .*

Proof. If $d \mid m$ and $d \notin \pi$, then the partition $(d^{m/d}) \notin D(\pi)$. But this contradicts the fact that π is full k -complete. □

3.1. Initial Full k -Complete Partitions

We isolate certain k -complete partitions which occur uniquely for certain minimal weights n .

Definition 5. The full k -complete partition with least weight is called the *initial full k -complete partition*.

n	k	$C_k(n)$
1	2	\emptyset
2	2	\emptyset
3	2	\emptyset
4	2	$(1^2, 2)$
5	2	$(1^3, 2)$
6	2	$(1^4, 2), (1^2, 2^2)$
7	2	$(1^5, 2), (1^3, 2^2), (1^2, 2, 3)$
7	3	\emptyset
8	2	$(1^6, 2), (1^4, 2^2), (1^3, 2, 3), (1^2, 2^3), (1^2, 2, 4)$
8	3	$(1^3, 2, 3)$
9	2	$(1^7, 2), (1^5, 2^2), (1^4, 2, 3), (1^3, 2^3), (1^3, 2, 4), (1^2, 2^2, 3), (1^2, 2, 5)$
9	3	$(1^4, 2, 3)$
10	2	$(1^8, 2), (1^6, 2^2), (1^5, 2, 3), (1^4, 2^3), (1^4, 2, 4), (1^3, 2^2, 3), (1^3, 2, 5), (1^2, 2^4), (1^2, 2, 3^2), (1^2, 2^2, 4), (1^2, 2, 6)$
10	3	$(1^5, 2, 3), (1^3, 2^2, 3)$
10	4	\emptyset

Table 2: Sets of full k -complete partitions, $C_k(n)$ for $1 \leq n \leq 10$ and $k = 2, 3$

Let the initial full k -complete partition be denoted by π_k , and let the initial full k -complete partition of n be $\pi_k(n)$.

For example, when $k = 1, 2, 3$, we have $\pi_1 = (1)$, $\pi_2 = (1^2, 2)$, $\pi_3 = (1^3, 2, 3)$.

If λ is any full k -complete partition, then by definition $\pi_k \in D(\lambda)$. So the intersection of all sets of derived partitions of full k -complete partitions is π_k .

From Lemma 1 we see that the initial full k -complete partition π_k depends on the divisors of all $m \in \{1, \dots, k\}$. By definition π_k does not contain all the divisors of $k + 1$; in particular it does not contain $k + 1$. The following lemma gives further characterizations of π_k , from which it may be computed. The proof may be deduced from Lemma 1.

Lemma 2. *The initial full k -complete partition π_k satisfies the following properties:*

- (i) *The partition π_k is equivalent to the multiset union of the sets of divisors of the integers $1, 2, \dots, k$. Thus if $V(n)$ denotes the set of divisors of n , then*

$$\pi_k \equiv \bigcup_{m=1}^k V(m). \tag{4}$$

- (ii) *Let $pV(m)$ denote the set of partitions of m into single divisors of m . Then π_k is obtained by selecting the parts with maximal multiplicity from the set $pV(1) \cup pV(2) \cup \dots \cup pV(k)$.*

Note that any $\lambda \in pV(m)$ has the form $\lambda = (d^{m/d})$. So we can write

$pV(m) = \{(1^{e_m}), (2^{e_m/2}), \dots, (m^{e_m/m})\}$, where $e_m \equiv m$, $e_m/d = 0$ if $d \nmid m$. Then

$$\pi_k \equiv \left(t^{\max(e_t/t, e_{t+1}/t, \dots, e_k/t)} \mid t = 1, 2, \dots, k \right). \tag{5}$$

Example 3. Since $V(m)$, $m = 1, 2, 3, 4$, are given by $\{1\}$, $\{1, 2\}$, $\{1, 3\}$, $\{1, 2, 4\}$ respectively, part (i) of Lemma 2 gives

$$\pi_4 \equiv (1) \cup (1, 2) \cup (1, 3) \cup (1, 2, 4) = (1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 2, 3, 4).$$

On the other hand, since $pV(m)$, $m = 1, 2, 3, 4$, are given by $\{(1)\}$, $\{(1^2), (2)\}$, $\{(1^3), (3)\}$, $\{(1^4), (2^2), (4)\}$ respectively, part (ii) of Lemma 2 gives

$$\pi_4 \equiv (1^{\max(1,2,3,4)}, 2^{\max(1,1,2)}, 3^{\max(1,0)}, 4^{\max(1)}) = (1^4, 2^2, 3, 4).$$

Proposition 2. *The weight w_k of π_k is given by*

$$w_k = \sum_{j=1}^k \sigma(j) = \sum_{r=1}^k r \left\lfloor \frac{k}{r} \right\rfloor, \tag{6}$$

where $\sigma(N)$ is the sum of divisors of N .

Proof. It follows from Equation (4), by taking the cardinalities of the sets, that $w_k = \sigma(1) + \sigma(2) + \dots + \sigma(k)$.

The second equality is a known identity (see for example [3]). However, note that for each integer m , the quantity $\lfloor \frac{k}{m} \rfloor$ counts the multiples of m not exceeding k , or equivalently, copies of m in the multiset of divisors of $1, 2, \dots, k$. So the full contribution of m to w_k is $m \lfloor \frac{k}{m} \rfloor$, and to π_k is $\lfloor \frac{k}{m} \rfloor$ copies of m or $m^{\lfloor \frac{k}{m} \rfloor}$. Hence π_k has the following explicit form, which is compatible with (5).

$$\pi_k = (1^k, 2^{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor}, 3^{\lfloor k/3 \rfloor}, \dots, \lfloor k/2 \rfloor^2, \lfloor k/2 \rfloor + 1, \lfloor k/2 \rfloor + 2, \dots, k). \tag{7}$$

By summing the parts of π_k we obtain the second equality in (6). □

From Proposition 2 we have $w_k = \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \sigma(j) + \sigma(k)$ which implies the recurrence

$$w_k = w_{k-1} + \sigma(k), \quad k > 0, \quad \text{with } w_0 = 0. \tag{8}$$

The sequence $\{w_k\}_{k \geq 1}$ begins as follows:

$$1, 4, 8, 15, 21, 33, 41, 56, 69, 87, 99, 127, 141, 165, 189, 220, 238, 277, \dots$$

This agrees with sequence A024916 in Sloane [11], wherein a comment describes the k -th term as “the total number of parts in all partitions of the positive integers less than or equal to k into equal parts”.

The following result may be deduced from the proof of Proposition 2, by summing up the multiplicities of π_k in (7).

Corollary 1. *The length ℓ_k of the initial full k -complete partition π_k is given by*

$$\ell_k = \sum_{j=1}^k \tau(j) = \sum_{r=1}^k \left\lfloor \frac{k}{r} \right\rfloor, \tag{9}$$

where $\tau(N)$ is the number of divisors of N .

Apart from (4), (5) and (7) π_{k+1} may be obtained from π_k using the following algorithm:

$$\text{“Insert the divisors of } k + 1 \text{ into } \pi_k\text{”} . \tag{10}$$

For example, since the divisors of 4 are 1, 2, 4, we have

$$\pi_4 = \pi_3 \cup (1, 2, 4) = (1^3, 2, 3) \cup (1, 2, 4) = (1^4, 2^2, 3, 4).$$

Since $C_1(n)$ is the set of partitions of n containing 1, we have $c_1(n) = p(n - 1)$. This fact is extended in the following statement.

Theorem 2. *The number of full k -complete partitions of n is given by $p(n - w_k)$:*

$$c_k(n) = p(n - w_k). \tag{11}$$

Proof. The number of partitions of n containing a positive integer r is given by $p(n - r)$ since we can remove one copy of r from a partition of n containing r to obtain an arbitrary partition of $n - r$.

By definition the multiset of parts of a full k -complete partition $\lambda \vdash n$ contains the multiset of the parts of π_k , that is, contains a partition of w_k . So we may replace the parts of π_k in λ with w_k to obtain a partition of n containing w_k . Hence, the result follows. \square

Theorem 2 implies the generating function (see for example, Andrews [2])

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} c_k(n)q^n = q^{w_k} \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1 - q^n}. \tag{12}$$

Remark 1. Denote the set of partitions of N by $P(N)$, i.e., $p(N) = |P(N)|$. The proof of Theorem 2 guarantees that $C_k(n)$ may be obtained by inserting the parts of π_k into partitions $\pi \in P(n - w_k)$ where π may be empty. For example, $C_2(8) = (2, 1^2) \cup P(4)$ gives:

$$\begin{aligned} C_2(8) &= (2, 1^2) \cup \{(1^4), (1^2, 2), (1, 3), (2^2), (4)\} \\ &= \{(1^6, 2), (1^4, 2^2), (1^3, 2, 3), (1^2, 2^3), (1^2, 2, 4)\} \quad (\text{cf. Table 2}). \end{aligned}$$

Equation (11) implies

$$c_k(n) - c_k(n - 1) = p(n - w_k) - p(n - 1 - w_k) = p(n - w_k)_{\geq 2},$$

where $p(N)_{\geq 2}$ is the number of partitions of N without 1's. This gives the following recurrence on which the construction of the rows of Table 2 is based:

$$c_k(n) = c_k(n - 1) + p(n - w_k)_{\geq 2}. \tag{13}$$

Thus to obtain $C_k(n)$ we either insert 1 into each $\pi \in C_k(n - 1)$ or merge the parts of π_k with the parts of any partition of $n - w_k$ that does not contain 1.

We can recover the generating function (12) from (13) as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (c_k(n - 1) + p(n - w_k)_{\geq 2}) q^n &= q^{w_k+1} \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1 - q^n} + q^{w_k} \prod_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1 - q^n} \\ &= q \cdot q^{w_k} \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1 - q^n} + q^{w_k} \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1 - q^n} (1 - q) \\ &= (q + (1 - q)) q^{w_k} \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1 - q^n} \\ &= q^{w_k} \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1 - q^n}. \end{aligned}$$

Lastly, we compare $p(0) + p(1) + \dots + p(k)$ with the cardinality of $D(\pi_k)$. Using (7) and Proposition 1 we get

$$|D(\pi_k)| = \prod_{j=1}^k \left\lfloor \frac{k+j}{j} \right\rfloor, \quad k > 1.$$

Note that $p(0) = 1$ counts the empty partition \emptyset of 0, and $p(0) + p(1) = 1 + 1 = 2$, including the partition (1). On the other hand, $D(\emptyset) = \{\emptyset\}$ and $D((1)) = \{\emptyset, (1)\}$. Hence $p(0) + p(1) + \dots + p(k) = |D(\pi_k)|$ when $k = 0, 1$. But when $k \geq 2$, we obtain the strong inequality

$$p(0) + p(1) + \dots + p(k) < |D(\pi_k)|, \quad k > 1. \tag{14}$$

Indeed the left side of (14) counts only partitions of $0, 1, \dots, k$. On the other hand, $|D(\pi_k)|$ counts all partitions of $0, 1, \dots, k$, and some partitions of $m, k+1 \leq m \leq w_k$:

$$D(\pi_k) = \bigcup_{j=1}^k P(j) \bigcup_{m=k+1}^{w_k} Q(m), \quad Q(m) \subset P(m).$$

In particular $\pi_k \in \bigcup_{m=k+1}^{w_k} Q(m) \neq \emptyset$.

The difference between the two quantities increases so rapidly that the following limit converges very fast to 0 (see Table 3).

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{p(0) + p(1) + \dots + p(k)}{\prod_{j=1}^k \lfloor \frac{k+j}{j} \rfloor} = 0.$$

k	$p(0) + \dots + p(k)$	$ D(\pi_k) $	$(p(0) + \dots + p(k))/ D(\pi_k) $
3	7	16	0.3750000000
4	12	60	0.1833333333
5	19	144	0.1250000000
6	30	672	0.04315476190
7	45	1536	0.02864583333
8	67	6480	0.01018518519
9	97	19200	0.005000000000
10	139	76032	0.001815025253
11	195	165888	0.001169463735
12	272	1048320	0.0002585088523

Table 3: $p(0) + \dots + p(k)$ versus $|D(\pi_k)|$ for some values of k

3.2. Strictly Full k -Complete Partitions

A partition π is said to be *strictly full k -complete* if π is full k -complete but not full $(k + 1)$ -complete. Thus $(1^2, 2, 3)$ is strictly full 2-complete and $(1^3, 2, 3, 4)$ is strictly full 3-complete. The partition $(1, 2^2, 3, 4, 5^2, 6, 7)$ is strictly full 1-complete. Every perfect partition is strictly full 1-complete.

By definition, every initial full k -complete partition is strictly full k -complete. The number $s_k(n)$ of strictly full k -complete partitions of n is given by

$$s_k(n) = |C_k(n) \setminus C_{k+1}(n)| = |C_k(n)| - |C_{k+1}(n)|.$$

Thus Equation (11) implies

$$s_k(n) = p(n - w_k) - p(n - w_{k+1}).$$

Hence using Equations (12) and (8) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} s_k(n)q^n &= (q^{w_k} - q^{w_{k+1}}) \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1 - q^n} \\ &= q^{w_k} (1 - q^{\sigma(k+1)}) \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1 - q^n}. \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

Thus if $f_t(n)$ denotes the number of partitions of n that do not contain t as a part, then

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} s_k(n)q^n = q^{w_k} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_{\sigma(k+1)}(n)q^n. \tag{16}$$

Hence we have proved the following partition theorem. But we also give a combinatorial proof below.

Theorem 3. *The number of strictly full k -complete partitions of n is equal to the number of partitions of $n - w_k$ which do not contain $\sigma(k + 1)$ as a part.*

Proof. Let $S_k(n)$ denote the set of strictly full k -complete partitions of n . In view of Equation (11), the set of full k -complete partitions of n is equinumerous with the set $P(n - w_k)$ of partitions of $n - w_k$, with a generally disjoint union:

$$C_k(n) = P(n - w_k) = S_k(n) \cup C_{k+1}(n). \tag{17}$$

The parts of each $\pi \in C_{k+1}(n)$ consist of all the divisors of $1, 2, \dots, k, k + 1$. Thus if $n < w_{k+1}$, then $C_{k+1}(n) = \emptyset$ and we simply have $S_k(n) = P(n - w_k)$, and clearly no contained partition in the right-hand-side of (17) can contain $\sigma(k + 1)$.

However, if $n \geq w_{k+1}$, we may replace the members of the set of divisors of $k + 1$ in $\pi \in C_{k+1}(n)$ with their sum $\sigma(k + 1)$. This transformation induces a bijection between $C_{k+1}(n)$ and the set of partitions of $n - w_k$ containing $\sigma(k + 1)$. This then produces $P(n - w_k) = S_k(n)$ provided we exclude partitions of $n - w_k$ containing the set of divisors of $k + 1$, which is in turn identified with partitions of $n - w_k$ containing $\sigma(k + 1)$. The result follows. \square

For example, from Table 2 we see that $C_2(7) = S_2(7) \cup C_3(7) = S_2(7)$ since $C_3(7) = \emptyset$; but

$$C_2(8) = S_2(8) \cup C_3(8) \equiv \{(1^6, 2), (1^4, 2^2), (1^2, 2^3), (1^2, 2, 4)\} \cup \{(1^3, 2, 3)\}.$$

Remark 2. Referring to Theorem 3, note that a partition $\pi \in S_k(n)$ may contain $\sigma(k + 1)$ as a part. For example, when $n = 10, k = 2$ and $\sigma(3) = 1 + 3 = 4$, we find in Table 2 that $(1^4, 2, 4), (1^2, 2^2, 4) \in S_2(10) = C_2(10) \setminus C_3(10)$, where $C_3(10) = \{(1^5, 2, 3), (1^3, 2^2, 3)\}$. However, by replacing 1 and 3 with 4 we obtain $C_3(10) = \{(1^5, 2, 3), (1^3, 2^2, 3)\} \mapsto \{(1^4, 2, 4), (1^2, 2^2, 4)\} \in S_2(10)$.

4. Perfect-Partition-Complete Partitions

A partition λ of a positive integer is called *perfect-partition-complete* for n (*pp-complete* for short) if the parts of λ contain all perfect partitions of n .

In other words, λ is pp-complete for n if $\pi \in D(\lambda)$ for every perfect partition $\pi \vdash n$.

As with k -complete partitions, there is an infinite number of pp-complete partitions for any positive integer n . For example, since the perfect partitions of 3 are (1^3) and $(1, 2)$, we see that any partition of the form

$$(1^a, 2^b, 3^{c_1}, 4^{c_2}, \dots), a \geq 3, b \geq 1, c_1 \geq 0, c_2 \geq 0, \dots,$$

is a pp-complete partition for 3.

The pp-complete partition for k with least weight will be called the k th *initial pp-complete* partition.

The k th initial pp-complete partition will be denoted by Λ_k , $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ (see the third column of Table 4). The contained perfect partitions are also given in the table (see the second column). For example, the following inclusion holds for $k = 7$:

$$\{(1^7), (1, 2^3), (1^3, 4), (1, 2, 4)\} \subset D((1^7, 2^3, 4)).$$

Many perfect partitions have the form $(1^{x-1}, x^y)$ for a fixed $x > 0$. Consequently $x \in \Lambda_{xy+x-1}$. For example, if $x = 3$, then $3 \in \Lambda_{3y+2}$, $y \geq 1$. This motivates the following statement.

Proposition 3. *Let k and t be positive integers with $k > t$. Then Λ_k contains t as a part if and only if $k \equiv -1 \pmod{t}$.*

Proof. We have

$$\begin{aligned} t \in \Lambda_k &\iff \text{there exists a perfect partition } \pi \vdash k \text{ with } t \in \pi \\ &\iff \text{there exists a factorization of the form } k + 1 = t \cdot v, v > 0 \\ &\iff \text{there exists a perfect partition of the form } \pi = (1^{t-1}, t^{v-1}) \vdash k. \end{aligned}$$

The weight of π is $t - 1 + t(v - 1) = tv - 1 = k$. Hence $k \equiv -1 \pmod{t}$. □

We consider few theorems concerning the initial pp-complete partitions in analogy to the theorems in Section 3.

Theorem 4. *The k th initial pp-complete partition has the explicit form:*

$$\Lambda_k = \left(d_1^{d_\tau-1}, d_2^{d_{\tau-1}-1}, \dots, d_{\tau-1}^{d_2-1}, d_\tau^{d_1-1} \right), \tau = \tau(k + 1). \tag{18}$$

Proof. We give a constructive proof based on the bijection asserted by Theorem 1.

Let $\Lambda_k = (\lambda_1^{e_1}, \lambda_2^{e_2}, \dots, \lambda_r^{e_r})$, $\lambda_1 < \dots < \lambda_k$, $e_i > 0 \forall i$. Then we observe that, in general, the e_i are maximal among the multiplicities of distinct parts of perfect partitions of k . Such maximal multiplicities arise from perfect partitions of k whose corresponding ordered factorizations have at most two factors.

k	Perfect Partitions of k	Λ_k	$w(\Lambda_k)$
1	(1)	(1)	1
2	(1 ²)	(1 ²)	2
3	(1 ³), (1, 2)	(1 ³ , 2)	5
4	(1 ⁴)	(1 ⁴)	4
5	(1 ⁵), (1, 2 ²), (1 ² , 3)	(1 ⁵ , 2 ² , 3)	12
6	(1 ⁶)	(1 ⁶)	6
7	(1 ⁷), (1, 2 ³), (1 ³ , 4), (1, 2, 4)	(1 ⁷ , 2 ³ , 4)	17
8	(1 ⁸), (1 ² , 3 ²)	(1 ⁸ , 3 ²)	14
9	(1 ⁹), (1, 2 ⁴), (1 ⁴ , 5)	(1 ⁹ , 2 ⁴ , 5)	22
10	(1 ¹⁰)	(1 ¹⁰)	10
11	(1 ¹¹), (1, 2 ⁵), (1, 2 ² , 6), (1, 2, 4 ²), (1 ³ , 4 ²), (1 ⁵ , 6), (1 ² , 3 ³), (1 ² , 3, 6)	(1 ¹¹ , 2 ⁵ , 3 ³ , 4 ² , 6)	44
12	(1 ¹²)	(1 ¹²)	12

Table 4: The k th initial pp-complete partitions for $1 \leq k \leq 12$

To see this, note that the trivial factorization $k + 1 = 1 \cdot (k + 1)$ gives the maximal multiplicity in $(1^k) \in \Lambda_k$. Thus $e_1 = k$.

The 2-factorization $k + 1 = a_1 \cdot a_2$, $a_i > 1$ corresponds to $(1^{a_1-1}, a_1^{a_2-1}) \vdash k$ which gives the maximal string $a_1^{a_2-1}$ for all first factors a_1 . Correspondingly, the $a_2 - 1$ give the multiplicities in Λ_k from left to right. We find that each string $\lambda_i^{e_i}$ originates from a factorization of the form $\lambda_i \cdot (e_i + 1) = k + 1$.

This may be clarified with an example. Let $k = 7$. Then $\{a_1 a_2 \mid a_1 a_2 = 8\} = \{2 \cdot 4, 4 \cdot 2\}$, and the partitions corresponding to these two factorizations, together with $8 = 1 \cdot 8$, suffice to determine Λ_7 :

$$\begin{aligned} \{1 \cdot 8\} \cup \{2 \cdot 4, 4 \cdot 2\} &\mapsto \{(1^{8-1}), (1, 2^{4-1}), (1^3, 4^{2-1})\} \\ &= \{(1^7), (1, 2^3), (1^3, 4)\} \\ &\subset D((1^7, 2^3, 4)), \text{ with } \Lambda_7 = (1^7, 2^3, 4). \end{aligned}$$

More directly we can write:

$$\begin{aligned} (1 \cdot 8, 2 \cdot 4, 4 \cdot 2, 8 \cdot 1) &\mapsto (1^{8-1}, 2^{4-1}, 4^{2-1}, 8^{1-1}) \\ &= (1^7, 2^3, 4, \emptyset) \\ &= (1^7, 2^3, 4). \end{aligned}$$

To summarize the construction in general, let the increasing sequence of divisors of $k + 1$ be

$$d_1, d_2, d_3, \dots, d_{\tau(k+1)-1}, d_{\tau(k+1)}, \tag{19}$$

where $d_1 = 1$, $d_{\tau(k+1)} = k + 1$ with $d_i \cdot d_{\tau(k+1)-i+1} = k + 1$ for all i .

Then Λ_k has the stated general form. □

Corollary 2. *Let $\ell(\Lambda_k)$ denote the length, and let $w(\Lambda_k)$ denote the weight, of Λ_k . Then*

$$\ell(\Lambda_k) = \sigma(k + 1) - \tau(k + 1). \tag{20}$$

$$w(\Lambda_k) = (k + 1)\tau(k + 1) - \sigma(k + 1). \tag{21}$$

Proof. From Theorem 4 the number of parts is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \ell(\Lambda_k) &= (d_\tau - 1) + (d_{\tau-1} - 1) + (d_{\tau-2} - 1) + \cdots + (d_2 - 1) + (d_1 - 1) \\ &= (d_\tau + d_{\tau-1} + d_{\tau-2} + \cdots + d_2 + d_1) + (-1)\tau \\ &= \sigma(k + 1) - \tau(k + 1). \end{aligned}$$

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned} w(\Lambda_k) &= (d_\tau - 1)1 + (d_{\tau-1} - 1)d_2 + \cdots + (d_2 - 1)d_{\tau-1} + (d_1 - 1)d_\tau \\ &= d_\tau 1 + d_{\tau-1}d_2 + \cdots + d_2d_{\tau-1} + d_1d_\tau - (1 + d_2 + \cdots + d_{\tau-1} + d_\tau) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^{\tau(k+1)} (k + 1) - \sigma(k + 1) \quad \because d_i d_{\tau+1-i} = k + 1 \\ &= (k + 1)\tau(k + 1) - \sigma(k + 1). \end{aligned}$$

□

For example, let $k = 7$. Then

$$\sigma(8) - \tau(8) = (1 + 2 + 4 + 8) - |\{1, 2, 4, 8\}| = 15 - 4 = 11,$$

and from Table 4 we can verify that Λ_7 has 11 parts.

The sequence $\{w(\Lambda_k)\}_{k \geq 1}$ begins as follows:

$$1, 2, 5, 4, 12, 6, 17, 14, 22, 10, 44, 12, 32, 36, 49, \dots$$

This agrees with sequence A094471 in [11]. A comment also describes the k th term as “The sum of all parts minus the total number of parts of all partitions of $k + 1$ into equal parts”.

Corollary 3. *The cardinality of the set of derived partitions of Λ_k is given by*

$$|D(\Lambda_k)| = \prod_{d|(k+1)} d = (k + 1)^{\tau(k+1)/2}. \tag{22}$$

Proof. The first equality follows immediately on applying Proposition (1) to the explicit form (18). The second equality is a known identity (see, for example, Apostol [3]). □

5. Full-Perfect-Partition-Complete Partitions

A partition λ of a positive integer is said to be *full-perfect-partition-complete* for n (*fpp-complete* for short) if the parts of λ contain all perfect partitions of every integer from 1 to n .

In other words, λ is fpp-complete for n if $\pi \in D(\lambda)$ for every perfect partition π of $m \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$.

Again we concentrate on the k th *initial fpp-complete* partition, to be denoted by Π_k for $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

Since each Λ_k contains all perfect partitions of k , and Π_k contains all perfect partitions of all integers from 1 to k , it follows that Π_k contains all the partitions $\Lambda_k, k = 1, \dots, k$. So we can write:

$$\Pi_k = \Lambda_1 \hat{U} \Lambda_2 \hat{U} \dots \hat{U} \Lambda_k, \tag{23}$$

where $A\hat{U}B$ stands for taking every distinct part with maximum multiplicity between A and B . Note that the binary operation \hat{U} is associative.

The partitions Π_1, \dots, Π_{12} are given in Table 5 (see the second column). The corresponding lengths $\ell(\Pi_k)$ and weights $w(\Pi_k)$ appear in the third and fourth columns respectively.

k	Π_k	$\ell(\Pi_k)$	$w(\Pi_k)$
1	(1)	1	1
2	(1 ²)	2	2
3	(1 ³ , 2)	4	5
4	(1 ⁴ , 2)	5	6
5	(1 ⁵ , 2 ² , 3)	8	12
6	(1 ⁶ , 2 ² , 3)	9	13
7	(1 ⁷ , 2 ³ , 3, 4)	12	20
8	(1 ⁸ , 2 ³ , 3 ² , 4)	14	24
9	(1 ⁹ , 2 ⁴ , 3 ² , 4, 5)	17	32
10	(1 ¹⁰ , 2 ⁴ , 3 ² , 4, 5)	18	33
11	(1 ¹¹ , 2 ⁵ , 3 ³ , 4 ² , 5, 6)	23	49
12	(1 ¹² , 2 ⁵ , 3 ³ , 4 ² , 5, 6)	24	50

Table 5: The k th initial fpp-complete partitions for $1 \leq k \leq 12$

By comparing Tables 5 and 4 when $k = 7$ we find, for instance, that Equation (23) gives

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_7 &= (1)\hat{U}(1^2)\hat{U}(1^3, 2)\hat{U}(1^4)\hat{U}(1^5, 2^2, 3)\hat{U}(1^3)\hat{U}(1^7, 2^3, 4) \\ &= (1^7, 2^3, 3, 4). \end{aligned}$$

We observe the following immediate properties of Π_k , from Table 5:

- (1) Π_k contains all of the integers $1, 2, \dots, \lfloor \frac{k+1}{2} \rfloor$, for each $k \geq 5$.
- (2) The sequences $\{\ell(\Pi_k)\}_{k \geq 1}$ and $\{w(\Pi_k)\}_{k \geq 1}$ are monotone increasing.
- (3) The integer $k + 1$ is prime if and only if $\ell(\Pi_k) = \ell(\Pi_{k-1}) + 1$ and $w(\Pi_k) = w(\Pi_{k-1}) + 1$.

As in previous agendas we compute the formulas for $\ell(\Pi_k)$ and $w(\Pi_k)$.

Theorem 5. *The k th initial fpp-complete partition has the explicit form:*

$$\Pi_k = (1^k, 2^{\lfloor (k-1)/2 \rfloor}, 3^{\lfloor (k-2)/3 \rfloor}, \dots, \lfloor (k+1)/3 \rfloor^2, \lfloor (k+4)/3 \rfloor, \dots, \lfloor (k+1)/2 \rfloor). \tag{24}$$

Proof. Note that Π_k has the form

$$\Pi_k = (1^{e_1}, 2^{e_2}, 3^{e_3}, \dots, h^{e_h}, \dots, \lfloor (k+1)/2 \rfloor^1), \tag{25}$$

where $1 \leq h \leq \lfloor (k+1)/2 \rfloor$ and $e_h > 0$ for all h .

In order to determine the e_i we consider the system of sets of proper divisors of $2, 3, \dots, k+1$, and let $dV(r)$ denote the set of divisors of r . Let

$$DV(k) = \{dV(r) \mid 2 \leq r \leq \lfloor (k+1)/2 \rfloor\}.$$

Clearly $1 \in dV(r)$ for every r , and $\lfloor (k+1)/2 \rfloor \in dV(r)$ for some r . The parts of Π_k are obtained with the following rule:

*For each h select all occurrences of h as a proper divisor in $DV(k)$;
the number of occurrences is the multiplicity e_h .*

Since $1 \in dV(r)$ as a proper divisor, for all r , the multiplicity of 1 in Π_k is k .

But $2 \leq h \in dV(r)$ as a proper divisor if and only if $r = jh$, where $2 \leq j \leq \lfloor (k+1)/h \rfloor$. This implies that

$$h \in dV(r) \iff r = 2h, 3h, \dots, h \lfloor (k+1)/h \rfloor$$

which gives exactly $\lfloor (k+1-h)/h \rfloor$ instances. Therefore the multiplicity of h in Π_k is $e_h = \lfloor (k+1-h)/h \rfloor$.

It follows that the general form of Π_k is as stated. □

Remark 3. Besides (23) and (24), Π_{k+1} may be obtained from Π_k using the following algorithm (cf. (10)):

“Insert the proper divisors of $k + 2$ into Π_k ” .

For example, since the proper divisors of 6 are 1, 2, 3, we have

$$\Pi_5 = \pi_4 \cup (1, 2, 3) = (1^4, 2) \cup (1, 2, 3) = (1^5, 2^2, 3).$$

Similarly, $\Pi_6 = \pi_5 \cup (1) = (1^5, 2^2, 3) \cup (1) = (1^6, 2^2, 3).$

Corollary 4. *Let $\ell(\Pi_k)$ denote the length and $w(\Pi_k)$ the weight of Π_k . Then*

$$(i) \quad \ell(\Pi_k) = -k + \sum_{j=1}^k \tau(j + 1). \tag{26}$$

$$(ii) \quad w(\Pi_k) = \sum_{j=1}^k (\sigma(j + 1) - j - 1). \tag{27}$$

Proof. (i) We add the multiplicities in Equation (24) and obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \ell(\Pi_k) &= \sum_{h=1}^{s_k} \left\lfloor \frac{k+1-h}{h} \right\rfloor, \quad s_k = \left\lfloor \frac{k+1}{2} \right\rfloor \\ &= -s_k + \sum_{h=1}^{s_k} \left\lfloor \frac{k+1}{h} \right\rfloor \\ &= -s_k + \sum_{h=1}^{k+1} \left\lfloor \frac{k+1}{h} \right\rfloor - \sum_{h=s_k+1}^{k+1} 1 \\ &= -(k+1) + \sum_{h=1}^{k+1} \left\lfloor \frac{k+1}{h} \right\rfloor. \end{aligned}$$

Thus on applying the identity $\sum_{j=1}^k \tau(j) = \sum_{r=1}^k \left\lfloor \frac{k}{r} \right\rfloor$ (see Equation (9)) we obtain the desired formula.

(ii) Using Equation (24) the proof is similar to that of part (i). □

For example, let $k = 7$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \ell(\Pi_7) &= -7 + \tau(2) + \tau(3) + \tau(4) + \tau(5) + \tau(6) + \tau(7) + \tau(8) \\ &= -7 + 2 + 2 + 3 + 2 + 4 + 2 + 4 \\ &= 12. \end{aligned}$$

The sequence $\{w(\Pi_k)\}_{k \geq 1}$ begins as follows:

$$1, 2, 5, 6, 12, 13, 20, 24, 32, 33, 49, 50, 60, 69, 84, \dots$$

This agrees with sequence A153485 in Sloane [11]. A comment also describes the k th term as “The sum of all aliquot divisors of all positive integers $\leq k + 1$ ”.

Lastly, the following assertion is the result of applying the formula in Proposition 1 to the explicit form (24).

Corollary 5. *The cardinality of the set of derived partitions of Π_k is given by*

$$|D(\Pi_k)| = \prod_{h=1}^{s_k} \left\lfloor \frac{k+1}{h} \right\rfloor, \quad s_k = \left\lfloor \frac{k+1}{2} \right\rfloor.$$

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